

VIEWS ON IMPROVING NATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING BASED ON A COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH

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ANNOTATION: This article addresses the issue of improving the content of native language instruction and its competency-based approach. It also compares the opinions of renowned Russian and international scholars on this issue. Furthermore, the paper presents personal observations regarding the prospects for improving native language instruction.

Keywords: native language, instructional content, competency, linguistic concepts, methodological framework, linguistic didactics, communicative approach, creativity.

In countries with developed education systems and economies, such as Finland, Japan, Singapore, Russia, Korea, Germany, Switzerland, and China, great importance is attached to the teaching of the native language, indicating that improving the quality of education in the native language is acquiring a socio-economic and political character. This article examines the theoretical analysis of the content of instruction in the native language in Uzbekistan in general, and the content of instruction in the native language in primary school in particular, as well as its evolutionary and historical development. UNESCO's international concept of education emphasizes the organization of instruction in the native language based on a competency-based approach in the context of globalization and integration, the creation of effective methods and technologies for the creative activation of students' cognitive and mental activity, improving the quality of education, stimulating creative thinking, and the acquisition of socially useful knowledge [1; 4].

First, let's clarify the concept of native language teaching content, which implies a didactic system aimed at developing language knowledge, speech skills, and communicative competencies in students at a certain stage of their learning. It consists of a set of educational goals, objectives, teaching materials, methods, and tools, and serves to ensure the comprehensive development of the individual. According to B. Ziemukhamedov, according to the modern concept of education, the content of native language teaching is not limited to teaching grammatical knowledge, but also includes the development of students' speech activity, the formation of independent thinking, and preparation for social life. [11;29] Accordingly, the content of native language teaching consists of the following main components.

1. The theoretical component of language learning includes the fundamentals of phonetics and phonology, lexicology (vocabulary), grammar (morphology and syntax), and the rules of spelling and punctuation. This knowledge shapes students' understanding of the language system and serves as the theoretical basis for speech activity.

2. In the speech skills development component, the main goal of native language instruction is to develop students' speech competence, which includes such activities as listening comprehension, oral speech (speaking), reading, and writing. These skills are developed comprehensively.

3. Communicative competence is the ability of a primary school student to correctly and effectively use language in various situations. It includes speech culture, adherence to communication rules, and the ability to clearly and fluently express thoughts.

4. Cultural and social component. Through native language instruction, students develop respect for national values, understand the connection between language and culture, and acquire

the skills to communicate effectively in a social environment. Initially, we considered it appropriate to clarify the concepts of "educational content," including "native language instruction." According to UNESCO, "Education is the process of transmitting cultural, social, economic, and spiritual values, knowledge, and skills from generation to generation, as well as the development of the individual and his or her full integration into society" [2; 9]. UNESCO views education as a comprehensive process aimed at the comprehensive development of the individual not only as a scientist and a scientist, but also as a factor in the social, moral, and cultural development of the individual. It also emphasizes that education should create equal opportunities for every pupil and student, take into account the learning needs of each person, and embody the goals of sustainable development, human rights, peace, and democratic values in modern society [3; 6].

The content of education is not simply a set of linguistic information, but also a means of shaping the future generation. Instruction in the native language plays a key role in this process. Modern requirements always require a revision of the content of education, its enrichment based on national and universal values, and the introduction of new pedagogical approaches. The foundation of all existing educational systems is educational content. Educational content includes a set of knowledge, skills, qualifications, and moral values that must be passed on from generation to generation. In particular, teaching the native language, as an important area shaping national identity, culture, and thinking, has its own content and components. There are a wide variety of views, opinions, and ideas regarding the concept of the content of teaching the native language and its components. Russian educational scientist I. Yu. Lerner suggests considering educational content as part of a rich social experience, selected for study by pupils or students and intended for their assimilation, methodically processed [4; 186].

According to Professor K. Kasimova, the content of the native language consists of knowledge about the sound structure of the Uzbek language and the methods of expressing sounds in written speech (phonetic and graphic); about the transformation of words and the connections of words in a sentence (grammatical, i.e. morphological and syntactic); about the morphemic composition of a word and the methods of word formation (word formation); about the lexical-semantic group of words (lexicological); about the principles of correct writing of the Uzbek language and the use of punctuation marks (spelling and punctuation) [5; 96]. A. Gulomov and G. Nematov write that the content of teaching the native language is as follows: "It is impossible and not necessary to teach a high school student all the linguistic knowledge accumulated by mankind over the centuries. Therefore, one of the main issues is the selection of the most necessary knowledge from the native language. The main criterion for selecting knowledge from the native language is its level of usefulness and practical application. "We understand useful knowledge from the native language as knowledge that serves to develop in children the skills of literate writing, creative thinking, correct and fluent expression of thoughts in oral and written form in accordance with the conditions of speech, and which ensures their upbringing and development in the spirit of high human qualities" [6; 9]. Associate Professor G. Kh. Khamroev acknowledges that along with the concept of "educational content" of the native language, the term "educational material" is also used. In a broad sense, it is equivalent to the concept of "educational content", while in a narrow sense it is understood as a system of knowledge, skills and competencies that must be mastered to a certain degree, adapted to the level of proficiency of students. Educational content includes 1) curricula, 2) curricula, 3) textbooks and 4) teaching aids" [7; 26].

L.A. Krasnova asserts that "in modern scientific concepts, the content of education is presented as a complex, multifaceted didactic phenomenon, problematized by a multitude of coexisting concepts with different conceptual structures and defining a specific model of the educational

process" [8, pp. 35-36]. According to K. Mavlonova, "the content of education in the native language is based on the parallel teaching of all the features and laws of the language, from simple to complex, based on the need for practical application, that is, teaching taking into account the age characteristics and learning abilities of the student, whose grammatical knowledge is necessary within the framework of the speech topic for the acquisition of the skills and qualifications specified in the qualification requirements" [9; 44].

F.I. Buslaev writes: "It is impossible and unnecessary to teach a high school student all the linguistic knowledge accumulated by humanity over the centuries. Therefore, one of the main issues is the selection of the most essential knowledge from the native language. The primary criterion for selecting knowledge from the native language is its level of usefulness and practical application. We understand useful knowledge from the native language as knowledge that helps develop children's skills in literate writing, creative thinking, and the correct and fluent expression of thoughts in oral and written form in accordance with the conditions of speech, as well as ensuring their upbringing and development in the spirit of high human qualities" [10; 21].

The main factors determining the content of instruction in the native language include state educational standards, the age and psychological characteristics of students, curricula and textbooks, national and cultural values, social requirements, and scientific advances in pedagogy and linguistics. There are several fundamental concepts for developing the content of instruction in the native language. These concepts define the approaches to language teaching and provide various theoretical foundations for defining educational content. Below is information on the main existing concepts of the content of instruction in the native language, their founders, and characteristics. 1. Linguists such as Roman Jakobson and Leonard Bloomfield developed the fundamental slogan that the linguistic concept assumes the formation of instructional content based on the changing system of language and its rules. In instruction in the native language, the grammatical, phonetic, lexical, and semantic systems of language occupy a central place. The uniqueness of this concept lies in its attention to the structural and functional aspects of language, that is, it focuses on language study exclusively from a linguistic perspective. 2. The concept of communicative competence, founded by M.S. Romanov, V.V. Vodopyanov and others, recognizes the idea that the content of education should be taught not only theoretically, but also in accordance with its real communicative tasks in society, that is, language is a means of communication between people, therefore, the content of education should be focused on the development of communicative skills.

3. The functional-stylistic concept, advocated by scholars such as M.A. Kasko and L.I. Neretina, recognizes that content should be taught in accordance with various linguistic functions and styles. It assumes that students master different styles and genres. The cognitive (critical) concept, founded by Z. Freud and J. Piaget, places great emphasis on the process of cognition, thinking, and understanding during language learning. Educational content is focused on the acquisition of knowledge, the development of analytical thinking, and creative skills, the specifics of which are considered closely linked to the cognitive processes of language learning. The cultural-humanitarian concept of teaching the native language in Uzbekistan is aimed at teaching national culture, history, and traditions through the teaching of the native language. In this case, educational content includes the spiritual and moral values of the nation, and its specificity is manifested in the formation of educational content based on national ideas and spirituality. It can be concluded that teaching one's native language is not simply a matter of teaching language rules, but also a process of nurturing the individual, shaping their worldview, thinking, and aesthetic taste. Educational content and concepts based on modern pedagogical approaches make this process more

effective. However, for these reforms to be fully effective in practice, a systematic approach, advanced teacher training, and educational materials that meet modern requirements are necessary.

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